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An Ayurvedic Management of *Vataj Hridroga* –A Single Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Cardiovascular diseases comprise the most prevalent serious disorders in industrialized nation and are rapidly growing problem in developing nations. The percentage of all deaths secondary to cardiovascular disease is higher among women i.e 43% than among men i.e 37%.¹ Atherosclerosis remains the major cause of cardiovascular disorders. In *Ayurveda* there is very brief description of *Hridroga*, but based on its presentation we can correlate *Vataj Hridroga* with Coronary Artery Disease (CAD). This study highlights the potential efficacy of herbo-mineral formulations in the management of *Vataj Hridroga*. To analyse the effect *Ayurvedic* management of Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) with *Jawahar Mohra*, *Khamira Gawzaban Ambari* and *Pushkargugglu Vati*. This was a single case study. In this study a diagnosed patient of Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) was taken. There was significant improvement in the clinical sign and symptoms.

Keywords: Coronary Artery Disease, *Vataj Hridroga*, *Hridroga*, Atherosclerosis, *Jawahar Mohra*, *Khamira Gawzaban Ambari*, *Pushkargugglu Vati*.

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INTRODUCTION

The description of *Hridroga* in Ayurveda is fairly brief, yet today, cardiovascular illnesses are the most common serious conditions in industrialized nations and are a rapidly expanding concern in developing countries. There are 107 *Marmas* (vital parts) listed in Ayurvedic scriptures, while *Trimarmas* i.e *Basti* (Urinary System), *Hridayam* (Heart) and *Shira* (Head) are regarded as superior to all others; as they have *Pran* (Vitality) within them². Among these *Trimarmas*, *Hridaya* has its own significance because this is the site of *Chetna*. *Acharya Charak* explained about *Dashpranayatan* (10 Principal seats of life) in which the *Prana* are situated and Among the *Dashpranayatan* is *Hridaya*³. It is the *Mula* of *Manovahi Srotas* and a place of *Mana* (Mind)⁴, hence it is connected to our emotions and mental processes. *Rasa Dhatu* is required for *Preenan* (feeding)⁵ and *Hridaya* is regarded as the *Utpadak Mula* of *Rasavaha Srotas*⁶ via which *Rasa* circulates throughout the body and provides nutrition. Similarly, *Mula* of *Pranavaha Srotas* is interpreted as *Hridaya*⁷. The *Hridaya* is the supreme site of *Ojas* and the locus of consciousness, hence why physicians name it *Hridaya*, *Mahat*, or *Artha*⁸. Development of *Hridaya* takes place from the *Sara* (Essence) of *Rakta* and *Kapha Dosh*⁹.

Acharya Charaka and *Vagabhatta* have described five types of *Hridaya Rogas* while *Sushruta* has given only four varieties of *Hridrogas* with their specific symptoms. It appears that the disease entity having pain in cardiac region are grouped together as *Hridroga*. It is difficult to give exact correlation of C.A.D. in Ayurvedic classics but on the basis of the description it appears that various Anginas and C.A.D. are very close in description to *Vatika Hridroga*. There is similarity in timing, type, site of pain and symptomatology.

Case Study

57 years old married, female came into OPD on 12/01/2026 with history of intermittent pain in chest region triggered by moderate exercise since two months and was taking statins, antiplatelet agents & antihypertensive drugs.

History

As per the history given by the patient, she was a known case of essential hypertension since seven years and was on irregular medication and since last two months she developed intermittent symptom of chest pain which was triggered by moderate type of exercise for which she consulted to an allopathic physician and was investigated. After investigation she was diagnosed as a case of single vessel disease (SVD) and doctor advised her statins antiplatelet agents, antihypertensive drugs & nitrates. She did not find much relief and decided for *Ayurvedic* management and came in the OPD on 12/01/2026. She was a known case of hypertension with negative family history. Patient was taking all medication as

prescribed by the Allopathic physician. Patient was examined thoroughly with *Darshan* (Inspection), *Sparshan* (Palpation) and *Prashan* (History taking) *Pariksha*. Her *Prakriti* (Bodily constitution) was *Pitta Kaphaja*.

Clinical Examination:

Physical Examination

- Blood Pressure: 130/86 mm of Hg
- Pulse rate – 78/min.
- Respiratory rate – 17/min.
- Temperature – 98.0⁰ F
- Edema – Absent
- Pallor – Absent
- Icterus – Absent
- Clubbing – Absent

Ashtasthana Pariksha

- *Nadi* (Pulse) – *Pittaj*
- *Mootra* (Urine) - 4-5 times per day
- *Malam* (Fecal matter) - Normal
- *Jihwa* (Tongue) - *Nirama*
- *Sabdham* (Voice of patient) – Normal speech
- *Sparsham* (Tactilation) - *Samshitoshna*
- *Druk* (Eyes and Vision) - *Prakruta*
- *Akriti* (General body build) – *Madhyama*

Systemic Examination:

Systemic examination did not depicted any significant changes.

Investigations:

- **Lipid Profile** (08/10/2025) : Cholesterol - 210 mg/dl, Triglycerides - 154 mg/dl, HDL - 54.4 mg/dl, LDL - 112.46 mg/dl, VLDL - 32 mg/dl.
- **Coronary Angiography** (08/10/2025) : LAD - D1: Proximal 70-80% Stenosis.
- **Colour Doppler Echocardiography Report** (08/10/2025) : Mildly reduced LV systolic function, mild mitral regurgitation, Conc. LV Hypertrophy, LVEF 55%.

Treatment Regimen:

The treatment was carried out with the following medicines with dietary precautions for 21 days with follow up after every 7 days.

Table 1: Treatment Regimen (Internal Medication)

S.No.	Name of Formulation	Dosages	Ingredients	Reference
1	<i>Jawahar Mohra</i>	125 mg BD	<i>Manikya Pishti</i> (Ruby), <i>Pann Pishti</i> (Emerald), <i>Mukta Pishti</i> (Pearl), <i>Pravala Pishti</i> (Coral), <i>Shringa Bhasma</i> (Deerhorn Ash), <i>Sangeyashab Pishti</i> , <i>Swarn Bhasma</i> (Gold Ash), <i>Rajat Bhasma</i> (Silver Ash), <i>Daryai Naryal</i> (Coconut)	<i>Ras Tantra Sara & Sidha Prayoga Sangrah</i> ¹⁰
2	<i>Khamira Gawzaban Ambari</i>	10 gm BD	<i>Berg Gawzaban</i> (<i>Borago officinalis</i>), <i>Badranjboya</i> (<i>Melissa officinalis</i>), <i>Burada Sandal Safaid</i> (<i>Santalum album</i>), <i>Behman Surkh</i> (<i>Salvia haematodes</i>), <i>Kishneez Khushk</i> (<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>), <i>Tukhm Balangu</i> (<i>Lallemantia royleana</i>), <i>Ustukhuddus</i> (<i>Lavandula stoech</i>), Ambar (Ambergris) , Warq Nuqra (Silver Leaves) , Marwareed (Pearls) , Yaqoot (Ruby) & Zamarrud (Emerald)	<i>Ras Tantra Sara & Sidha Prayoga Sangrah</i> ¹¹
3	<i>Pushkargugglu Vati</i>	2 tab. BD	<i>Pushkarmoola</i> (<i>Inula racemosa</i>), <i>Guggulu</i> (<i>Commiphora wightii</i>)	<i>Anubhuta Yoga</i>

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

This regimen was advised twice in a day with Luke warm water and was instructed to avoid extra salt, tea, coffee, spicy, fried and heavy food. The patient was advised to continue on going allopathic treatment alongside the current therapeutic regimen. The aforementioned regimen was continued for a duration of two months, resulting in symptomatic relief.

DISCUSSION:

In this patient the cause of *Hrutshoola* (Chest Pain) was due to *Meda Avruta Vata i.e Avrana Janya Samprapti*. The *Samarasa* is responsible for *Medodushti* (Dyslipidaemia). But according to Charaka, Sushruta and Vagabhatta, in the context of *Hridroga Samprapti*, more emphasis is on *Rasadushti*. So we can say that the hyperlipidaemic state (*Sama Rasa*), definitely causes *Rasadushti*. In this stage alteration of the functions of lipoprotein occurs i.e. oxidation of lipoproteins (dyslipidaemia).

The *Rasa* has a tendency of *Srotorodha* (Obstruction of channels), *Gaurava* (Feeling of heaviness of the body) etc. Whenever it mixes with vitiated *Doshas* (mainly *Vata*) and circulates all over the body and enters into the heart and *Dashadhamanis* (affected arteries), causes the monocyte accumulation aggregation of lipoproteins, foam cell, atheroma formation and finally develops Atherosclerosis or *Dhamanipratichaya*. This Atherosclerosis whenever causes the *Sanga* (obstruction) of *Pranavaha Srotas* and *Rasavaha Srotas* produce *Vataj Hridroga*.

Probable mode of action of *Jawahar Mohra & Khamira Gawzaban Ambari*

The therapeutic response observed in this case may be attributed to the synergistic pharmacological action of *Jawahar Mohra* and *Khamira Gawzaban Ambari*, which together enhance cardiogenic activity promote overall systemic stability & alleviate the aggravated *Vata* by its property of *Srotoshodhana* and by doing so the path for the movement of *Vata* will be cleared which ultimately leads to *Vata Anulomana* thereby providing relief from chest pain.

Probable mode of action of *Pushkargugglu Vati*

Pushkarmoola and *Guggulu* exert their therapeutic effects by pacifying *Vata-Kapha*, *Srotoshodhana*, and *Agni Deepana*. By facilitating the clearance of *Srotoshodha* and improving metabolic and circulatory functions, they play a significant role in alleviating chest pain and restoring systemic balance

CONCLUSION:

In this patient the *Samprapti* ends in *Meda Avruta Vata* results obstruction of coronary blood vessels result in chest pain. In this study the entire regimen was planned according to *Dosha* predominance and to target the *Samprapti Vighatana*. This study highlights the efficiency of above mentioned Ayurvedic herbo-mineral formulation in the effective management of *Vataj Hridroga*. In Ayurveda, effective management of any *Vyadhi* requires a thorough understanding of its *Samprapti*. Accordingly, treatment is planned on the principles of *Samprapti Vighatana*.

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